

***Ueckermanniella* nom. nov. pro *Kakamasia* Ueckermann et Grout, 2007 (Acari, Iolinidae) nec *Kakamasia* Lawrence, 1944 (Acari, Erythraeidae)**

Petar BERON

BERON P. 2012. *Ueckermanniella* nom. nov. pro *Kakamasia* Ueckermann et Grout, 2007 (Acari, Iolinidae) nec *Kakamasia* Lawrence, 1944 (Acari, Erythraeidae). – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, **20**: 67-68.

Key words: Acari, Iolinidae, Erythraeidae, South Africa, homonymy, new names

UECKERMANN & GROUT (2007) described a new genus from South Africa called *Kakamasia* (Iolinidae). However, this name has been used by LAWRENCE (1944), who described the genus *Kakamasia* (Erythraeidae), again from South Africa. Therefore, here we propose (with the consent of Dr. E. A. Ueckermann) a replacement name *Ueckermanniella* nom. nov. for *Kakamasia* Ueckermann et Grout, 2007 and a new combination *Ueckermanniella cataracta* (Ueckermann et Grout, 2007).

References

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- UECKERMANN E.A., GROUT T.G. 2007. Tydeoid mites (Acari: Tydeidae, Edbakerellidae, Iolinidae) occurring on *Citrus* in southern Africa. – *Journal of Natural History*, **41** (37-40): 2351-2378.

Received: 11.11.2011

Author's address:

Petar Beron, National Museum of Natural History – BAS, Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd. 1, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

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Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

Установена е хомонимия между родовите имена *Kakamasia* Ueckermann et Grout, 2007 (Acari, Iolinidae) nec *Kakamasia* Lawrence, 1944 (Acari, Erythraeidae), и двете от Южна Африка. Предлага се по-новият хомоним да се замени с *Ueckermanniella* nom. nov. *Ueckermanniella cataracta* (Ueckermann et Grout, 2007).